

ISic4386

A fragmentary monumental Latin inscription

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Ietas

Place of origin (modern)

Monte Iato

Provenance

From material recovered from the interior of the large Hellenistic public cistern to the west of the agora

Coordinates

37.966871, 13.197718

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Monte Iato, Monte Iato excavation, inventory I.16

Physical Description

A block of worked limestone. The block is broken on the left; on the right margin the remains of 'anathyrosis' indicate that the edge of the stone is intact, but that a further block was joined to this one. The upper and lower margins are preserved.

Dimensions

Height 42 cm

Width 49 cm

Depth 32 cm

Layout

Parts of two lines of monumental Latin letters are preserved, which fill most of the available face.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Plainly carved monumental letters without serifs.

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 100 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [---]ti(vac.undefined)ma[---]

2. [---]dosin[---]

Apparatus

Text from photograph of Isler 2009: taf.16.9

Isler -]T(?)TIMA; the trace of an upper horizontal is visible, but this could be compatible with F or E also

Translation

Commentary

As Isler observes, the nature of the blocks and the lettering mean that this must be part of a monumental text (from a building?), not dissimilar to those found in the theatre. The reading is not entirely clear, and the significance of DOSIN in a Latin text is very unclear (perhaps the end of a Greek name rendered in Latin?). On the basis of both architectural form and lettering, Isler reasonably suggests a late Republican date.

Digital identifiers:

EDCS 74000028

Bibliography

Isler, H. P. 2009. Grabungen auf dem Monte Iato im Herbst 2007 und im Jahr 2008. *Antike Kunst*. 52: 95-109. At 101 with taf.16.9

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-21): ISic4386. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4381870>

Scan of Isler 2009: taf.16.9